

On a Novel Reinforcement Corresponding to Stress Lines

Horst R o t h e

Institute of Polymer Research Dresden / Germany

Abstract

Fabrics and prepreg tapes are used as semi-finished products for reinforcing of highly stressed composites. For certain components both show disadvantages like waste generation by cutting of the webs or/and by the necessity of manual labour. Besides, often the reinforcing filaments which only are able to bear stresses run in the wrong direction because their direction is defined by the structure of the fabrics.

Innovatively a novel type of multi-axial reinforcement was created. After that, the reinforcing filaments which are combined to roving-like threads can freely be fixed on a thin and flexible base material in the way you like. The base material is integrated into the component.

Examples of this novel system are shown: a radially reinforced disk, an example for a frame with a strut, and a local supplementary reinforcement for a T-like branching. For demonstration purposes the threads were wound by thin copper wires. Thus, their direction could be made visible by X-raying.

Introduction

For reinforcing of composites different textile reinforcements are well known, like nonwovens (mats), woven fabrics (plain and 3D), stitch-bonded fabrics (e.g. system LIPA or MALIMO). For special purposes warp and weft knitted fabrics are applied, and certain highly stressed components are reinforced by braiding systems.

The meeting "New Textiles for Composites", which took place on December 9-10, 1992, in LEUVEN/Belgium, [1] gave a survey on these materials. For details papers of WULFHORST [2], VERPOEST [3], and KO [4] are mentioned.

Present State

The fabrics mentioned above are produced as webs, i.e. they have a certain width and a high length which is necessary for efficient and cheap manufacturing.

The users make cuts and fit them to the special shape of the desired component, and several or many cuts of the same or of different fabrics are applied for building up the required thickness.

Making cuts is connected with waste of reinforcement fabrics. The more expensive the materials the more disadvantageous is this technology.

The threads of these fabrics usually run in preferred directions: along, across and/or bias. Thus, the threads which are only able to bear stresses are often arranged in a wrong direction. Polar diagrams of tensile strength show this typical behaviour.

Another method for arranging the reinforcements is based on prepreg types. Complicatedly shaped components can optimally be reinforced in this way. But this manufacturing requires a lot of manual labour and is preferably applied for high-performance laminates.

Imperfections

In commercial fabrics the direction of threads is defined. Thus, they meet the requirements of the stress analysts only partly for certain components.

The waste mentioned above is significant especially for frame-like components if fabrics are used. And this waste can be an expensive material which in the end contaminates the rubbish dumps. In addition, T-branchings, typical when struts exist, are problematic with regard to a deflection of stress lines "round a corner".

Thus, for special requirements it can be useful to have semi-finished products containing reinforcing filaments adapted to the shape of a component and corresponding to the main stress lines.

Innovation

In order to avoid these imperfections a novel type of multi-axial reinforcement was innovatively created [5]. Reinforcing filament yarns or roving-like threads are fixed on a thin and flexible base material. They can be arranged in any direction you like, that means to and fro, ahead and back, or crisscross. Thus, the reinforcing material can be laid according to the component shape and following the main stress lines. When forming the composite the base material is integrated.

These reinforcements are not produced continuously as a web, but they are made like individual pieces exactly fitted to the requirements of a component. The applied technology is NC-controlled and suitable for serial production, in principle. A change of the design is easy to manage.

As everybody knows the arrangement of the reinforcing filaments is but badly to recognize in a composite. For a representation the roving-like threads were wound with thin copper wires. In this way the structure of the textile reinforcements could be made visible by X-raying. The Figures 1 to 3 show reduced positives of these X-ray photograms.

Fig. 1 is a disk radially reinforced, Fig. 2 shows an example of a frame with a strut, and Fig. 3 represents a local supplementary reinforcement for a T-like branching.

These figures may only give a small idea on the large variety of designs which are possible.

The roving-like threads can, in principle, consist of glass, carbon or aramide, and these novel reinforcements can be applied for thermoplastics and for thermosettings as well. But thermoplastics should be preferred because of the well-known problems of plastic recycling. In our experiments we have been working with commingled yarns based on glass and polyamide filaments, and with carbon fibres and PEEK filaments. The base material must be adapted to these matrix materials, of course.

Remarks to the Poster

The poster illustrates the novel reinforcements described above, and real samples are shown. This exposition represents an offer to structural engineers for realizing of highly stressed components based on a new approach.

Final Remarks

The described method permits manufacturing of semi-finished products with multi-axial reinforcements corresponding to stress lines. To realize definite components a close cooperation between engineers and "reinforcement designers" is advisable.

References

- [1] "New Textiles for Composites". Meeting December 9-10, 1992, organized by the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (Belgium).
- [2] Wulfhorst, B., et al.: Three-dimensional Textiles for Use in Fibre-reinforced Composite Materials. *Kunststoffe German Plastics* 81 (1991) 11, p. 16-17.
- [3] Verpoest, I. et al.: Research in Textile Composites at K.U.LEUVEN. Paper of the meeting [1].
- [4] Ko, F.K.: Preform Fiber Architecture for Ceramic-matrix Composites. *Ceramic Bulletin*, 68 (1989) 2, p. 401-414.
- [5] DE - P 42 14 636.4: Formbares, multiaxiales Verstärkungsgebilde.

Fig. 1: Disk with radial reinforcement
(Reduced positive of an X-rayed photogram)

Fig. 2: Example of reinforcement of a frame with a strut

Fig. 3: Local supplementary reinforcement for a T-like branching

OPTIMISATION

